

TILSHUNOSLIKDA HAMDARDLIKKA OID BIRLIKLAR TAHLILI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada hamdardlik konsepti va uning dunyo tilshunosligida qaysi olimlar tomonidan o'rganilganlik darajasi yoritib berilgan. Shuningdek, hamdardlik nutq akti va uning mashhur olim Elvud tomonidan kategoriyalarga ajratilgani ko'rishimiz mumkin. Bundan tashqari, dunyo tadqiqotchi olimlarining Elvud kategoriyalaridan foydalanib, hamdardlikka oid birliklarni tahlil asosida yoritib bergani haqida ma'lumotlar aks etgan.

Kalit so'zlar: hamdardlik, hamdardlikka oid iboralar, hamdardlik kategoriyalari pragmatika, nutq akti.

Fikrimizcha, hamdardlikka oid birliklar dunyo miqyosida o'rganilishi va unga tilshunos olimlarning tomonidan berilgan ta'riflarni keltirishdan oldin, "hamdardlik" so'zining lug'aviy ma'nosiga e'tibor qaratish maqsadga muvofiq bo'lar edi. Leonard Zunin va Hilari Stenton Zunin o'zlarining "The Art of Condolence" kitobida "The origin of the word condolence holds a profound message. There are two Latin roots: com, meaning "together," and dolere, meaning "to grieve" ya'ni "hamdardlik" so'zining kelib chiqishi chuqur ma'noni bildiradi. Uning ikkita lotin ildizi bor ya'ni com "birgalikda" dolere "qayg'urmoq" ma'nolarini anglatadi¹ deya hamdardlik so'zining kelib chiqishi haqida fikrlarini bildiradilar. Shuningdek, o'zbek tilining izohli lug'atida hamdardlikka quyidagicha ta'rif beriladi: 1) kimsaning g'am-qayg'usi, dardiga sheriklik, birgalik his tuyg'usi, shunday his tuyg'uli holat; 2) yaxshi gaplar bilan kimsaning dardini, xafaligini yozishga unga tasalli berishga urinmoq, taskin bermoq; 3) ko'ngil ko'tarish uchun, yaqin kimsasi o'lgan kishining qayg'usiga sherik ekanligini bildirmoq.²

Shu bilan birgalikda, ingliz tilida hamdardlik "condolence" deyiladi va uning turli xil sinonimlari mavjud. Misol uchun: commiseration, grieve, sympathy, consolation, compassion, solace and empathy kabi. Cambridge lug'atida "hamdardlik" so'ziga 1) sympathy and sadness for the family or close friends of a person who has recently died, or an expression of this, especially in written form (condolence); 2) an expression of understanding and care for someone else's suffering (sympathy); 3) the ability to share someone else's feelings or experiences by imagining what it would be like to be in that person's situation (empathy); 4) to express sympathy to someone about some bad luck (commiserate)³ deb ta'rif bergan.

¹ Zunin L.M., and Zunin H.S. The Art of Condolence: What to write, what to say, what to do at a time of loss. New York, NY: Harper Collins publishers, 1991. P 6

² O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati H-harfi. "O'zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi" Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti. Toshkent. B 497-498

³ <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/commiserate>

Shuningdek, tadqiqot ishimizda sympathy (hamdardlik), empathy (empatiya) va condolence (ta'ziya) terminlariga aniqlik kiritib, ularni farqlarini ajratib olishimiz kerak.

Insonlar hayotining ma'lum bir nuqtasida masalan, ma'raka, yaqin insoni vafot etishi, og'ir hastalikka chalinish, ishdan bo'shatilish, oilaning buzilishi, inqirozga uchrash kabi vaziyatlarda o'z hamdardligini ma'lum bir so'z, ibora va birikmalar bilan ifodalaydi. Xuddi shuningdek, ingliz va o'zbek madaniyatida ham bu kabi so'z, ibora va birliklar mavjud. Kishining yaqin insoni vafot etganda ularga aytiladigan hamdardlik, ularni biroz bo'lsada ko'ngliga huzur baxsh etishga, yupatishga hamda judolikdan azoblanayotgan qalbiga taskin topishga biroz bo'lsada yordam beradi. Bunday kunda odamlar juda g'amgin bo'lishadi va sizning bildirgan ta'ziyangiz sizni ular bilan birga ekanligingiz va o'sha insonlarni qo'llab-quvvatlashingizni anglatadi. Quyida keltirilgan L.Zuninning qarashlari ham yuqoridagi fikrlarimizni tasdiqlaydi. "Condoling actions reaffirm our bonds to humanity; they strengthen and enlarge each of us. Each word of comfort, each letter of condolence, each act of helpful service has the potential to serve not only as a message of sympathy but as a song of compassion and truth"⁴. Hamdardlik bildirish insoniyatga bo'lgan rishtalarimizni yana bir bor tasdiqlaydi; ular har birimizni kuchli va bag'ri keng qiladi. Har bir bildirilgan tasalli so'zi, har bir ta'ziya maktubi, har bir berilgan astoyidil yordam nafaqat hamdardlik xabari, balki rahmshafqat va haqiqat qo'shig'i sifatida xizmat qilish imkoniyatiga ega.

Ta'ziya (arab. – yupatish, hamdardlik bildirish)- azador kishiga tasalli berish, ahvoli so'rash odati.⁵

Mixalskaning ta'rifiga ko'ra "sympathy (from the Greek words syn "together" and pathos "feeling" which means "fellow-feeling") is the perception, understanding and reaction to be distress or need for another life form" ya'ni bizning talqinimizda "simpatiya (yunoncha syn "birga" va pathos "hissiyot" so'zlaridan kelib chiqqan bo'lib, "birgalikda his qilish" degan ma'noni anglatadi) – bu qayg'u yoki boshqa hayot shakliga muhtojlikni idrok etish, tushunish va reaksiyadir". Arak universiteti professori Dr. Hamidreza Dovlatabadi o'zining "Eron va ingliz so'zlashuvchilari marosimlarida qo'llaydigan hamdardlik va ta'ziya birliklari qiyyosiy tahlili"⁶ deya nomlangan maqolasida, empatiya va hamdardlik tushunchalari ko'pincha o'zaro almashinib ishlatilishi haqida so'z yuritadi va ikki termin ham kelib chiqishi va ma'no jihatdan farq qilishini tushuntirib o'tadi. Empatiya - bu ma'lum bir emotsional holatni biror kishi bilan bo'lishish va tushunishdir deydi. Simpatiya esa ma'lum bir emotsional holatni bo'lishishni talab etmaydi, aksincha hamdardlik boshqa bironing hotirjamligi, farovonligi haqida qayg'urish deya ta'kidlab o'tadi.

Dunyo miqyosida hamdardlikka oid birliklar ustida bir qancha ilmiy ishlar amalga oshirilgan va uning turli lingvistik jihatlari dunyo olimlari va tadqiqotchilari tomonidan tahlil qilingan.

Hamdardlik mavzusiga oid tadqiqotlar dunyo tilshunosligida kamdan-kam uchraydi bu tushuncha haqidagi izlanishlar amerikalik va yaponiyalik ishtirokchilar o'rtasida hamdardlik

⁴ Zunin L.M., and Zunin H.S. The Art of Condolence: What to write, what to say, what to do at a time of loss. New York, NY: Harper Collins publishers, 1991. P 6

⁵ Murodova F. Turk tilida ta'ziya bilan bog'liq hamdardlik ma'nosini ifadolovchi birliklar talqini. Ta'lim fidoylari, Mart 2022. B 109

⁶ Dowlatabedi H., Mashhadi J. Comparative study of Sympathy and Condolences Use by Iranian and English native speakers in ceremonies: (a conversation analysis study). Tehran University, 2018. P 6

bildirish usullarini taqqoslagan olim Elvud tomonidan boshlab berilgan. U o'z tadqiqotida **Discourse Completion Task (DCT)** – nutqni yakunlash vazifasi deb nomlangan usuldan foydalanadi.⁷ Elvud shuningdek, ishtirokchilardan ta'ziya paytida qanday qilib hamdardligini bildirishini ifodalash va qatnashuvchilarga ikkita vaziyat taqdim etiladi. Avvaliga Elvud bu tadqiqotni Olshteyn va Kohen⁸ tomonidan topilgan besh toifaga bo'lingan semantik formula asosida tahlil qiladi.

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⁷ Ching H. K. Functions of Malaysian Condolences Written in Text Messages. *Pertanika, Journal of Social Science and Humanities*. June, 2015. P 6

⁸ Olshtain, E., & Cohen, A. (1983). *Apology: A speech act set*. In N. Wolfson & E. Judd (Eds.), *Sociolinguistics and language acquisition* (pp. 18-35). Rowley, MA: Newbury House